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Role of Personality on Adult Criminals Going Through Imprisonment

Abstract

Crime is an act of violence and aggression against not only an individual but also against the society as a whole. Personality refers to individual differences in characteristic patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. The study of personality focuses on two broad areas: One understands individual differences in particular personality characteristics, such as sociability or irritability. The other understands how the various characteristics of a person come together as a whole. The present research is to study the role of different personality types among adult criminals. The primary objective is to study and compare the role of personality along with its different dimensions (Decisiveness, Responsibility, Emotional Stability, Masculinity, Friendliness, Heterosexuality, Ego-Strength, Curiosity, Dominance, Self-concept) between the Gender (male criminals and female criminals). The second objective is to study and compare the role of personality along with its different dimensions between the Types of crime (high charged and low charged criminals). The third objective is to find out an interaction effect between gender and the type of crime in criminals with regards to the role of personality. Sample size comprised of 120 criminals, 60 males and 60 females. The data was collected by two stage stratified random sampling method from a local jail. The tool used was Differential Personality Inventory Scale by Arun Kumar Singh and Ashish Kumar Singh (1971) which has 150 items. The anticipated result of the study indicates a significant difference among male criminals and female criminals on personality. Males were more prone to crime than females.

Keywords: *Crime, personality, gender, type of crime, criminal*

Introduction

Crime refers to violence and aggression against not only an individual but also against the whole society. There are mainly three types of crime: Felonies, Misdemeanours, and Violations. Criminology is the scientific study of crime. Criminology includes its causes, reactions by law implementation and procedure of redressal. Criminology is the specific study of crime from diverse

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perspectives; the first is legal, second is political, third is sociological, and last one is psychological.

2018 National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), report shows that crime in India has risen. The report comprises that the cases of murder, rapes, and kidnapping have seen a rise. The official data of the *Times of India* describe that the cases of murder, abduction, rape, dowry death, and fatal accidents have seen an augment as compared to the 2017. In 2016, according to the National Crime Records Bureau data, total crimes by criminals were recorded to be 2.97 million and the crime rate was found to be 379 crimes per lakh population. The cases of molestation are mildly less from 378 cases in 2017 to 315 cases in last year. According to 2017, Global Peace Index report, India is the fourth most dangerous country for women travellers. The latest data given from the Delhi police under the Central government, data describe for 2017 and 2018, from 1 to May 15 in both years, show a drop in the total number of heinous crimes in Delhi by roughly **5.6%**. Moreover, the reported cases of rape alone have increased from 757 to 780.

According to former Union minister for Women and Child Development, Renuka Chowdhury, around 70 per cent of women in India are victims of domestic violence. The National Crime Records Bureau describe that a crime against a woman is committed in every three minutes, and a woman is raped every 29 minutes, a death occurs due to dowry in every 77 minutes, and one case of cruelty committed by either the husband or relative of the husband occurs every nine minutes.

According to the American Psychological Association, Personality refers to the individual differences in attribute patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. The study of personality focuses on two types of big areas: Firstly, understanding individual differences in particular personality attributes, such as sociability or irritability. Secondly, understanding how the others characteristics of a person come together as a whole.

According to Freud, children develop from series of stages during which the libidinal energy of the id becomes focused on specific erogenous zones. Successful completion of each stage describes in moving on to the next phase of development, but failure at any particular stage can result in fixations that can impact adult personality. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs describes the importance of self-actualization and is often pictured as a pyramid. The base of the pyramid consists of basic survival needs, while the top of the pyramid is focused on self-actualizing needs.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study and compare the role of personality along with its different dimensions (Decisiveness, Responsibility, Emotional Stability, Masculinity, Friendliness, Heterosexuality, Ego-Strength, Curiosity, Dominance, Self-concept) between two different Genders (male criminals and female criminals).
2. To study and compare the role of personality along with its different dimensions (Decisiveness, Responsibility, Emotional Stability, Masculinity, Friendliness, Heterosexuality, Ego-Strength, Curiosity, Dominance, Self-concept) between the Types of crime (high charged and low charged criminals).
3. To find out an interaction effect between gender and the type of crime in criminals with regards to the role of personality.

Hypotheses

Considering the aims of the present research study, following hypotheses have been formulated.

1. There will be no significant difference between Male Criminals and Female Criminals (gender) with regards to personality.
2. There will be no significant difference between high charged criminals and low charged criminals (types of crime) with regards to personality.
3. There will be no significant interaction effect between gender and Types of Crime with regards to personality.

Crime and Gender Difference

Females are arrested less than males for all categories of crime except prostitution. According to the available data this ratio is true for all countries. In 2014, 73% Females were arrested in the US and 80.4% of men were arrested for violent crime and 62.9% of men were arrested for property crime.

According to the reports given by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, worldwide, the ratio of homicide victims of male are high, which is approximately 78.7%. Furthermore, 193 out of 202 countries, males were more likely to be killed than females. According to 2013 global study, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime found that 96% males accounted for all homicides perpetrators worldwide.

Different types of Crime

Felonies are considered to be the most serious crimes. In this crime, criminals are punishable for one year or more of imprisonment. This crime includes

personal crimes, such as murder, robbery and rape. Other types of crimes are against property, which includes burglary or larceny. Misdemeanours crime are considered to be less serious crimes. Under this category criminals are punishable by less than one year of imprisonment. This category of crime includes assault, battery or writing bad checks. Violations are again considered to be less serious crime than misdemeanours crime. It includes traffic violations. Some sexual crimes such as incest, sodomy, indecent exposure or exhibitionism are a part of it.

Methodology

Aim: The aim of this research is to study the role of different personality types among adult criminals in relation to severity of crime and gender.

Sample

The aim of the present research study is to investigate the effect of personality of the criminals. Keeping this purpose in view sample selection was carried out. The study has been taken for 2 groups of criminals. The total sample comprised of 120 criminals (males=60, females=60). The sample was randomly selected from the Sabarmati Central Jail Ahmedabad.

Tool

Differential Personality Inventory Scale by Arun Kumar Singh and Ashish Kumar Singh. (1971) with its different dimensions (Decisiveness, Responsibility, Emotional Stability, Masculinity, Friendliness, Heterosexuality, Ego-Strength, Curiosity, Dominance, Self-concept). This inventory contains 150 items.

Study design

The following study was quantitative in nature. The data collected was measured in a statistical format using 2×2 ANOVA test. The structure was in the form of a randomised design.

Statistical Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing the mean score of Gender (Male and Female) and Types of crime (High crime and Low crime) with relation to Differential Personality Inventory Dimension.

	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>High crime</i>	<i>Low crime</i>
		A1	A2	B1	B2
1	Decisiveness	8.9	9.1333	9.15	8.8833
2	Responsibility	8.9667	8.9833	9.3167	8.6333

(Contd...)

3	Emotional Stability	9.8166	8.25	9.3666	8.7
4	Masculinity	9.1	7.6	8.5	8.2
5	Friendliness	9.1833	7.7	8.95	7.9333
6	Heterosexuality	7.7333	6.8833	7.9	6.7166
7	Ego-Strength	9.9333	9.0333	10.2	8.7666
8	Curiosity	8.5166	7.9	8.4166	8
9	Dominance	9.2166	8.3333	8.9666	8.5833
10	Self-Concept	8.5	7.9	8.7	7.7

(n=120, males=60, females=60)

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing the Mean score of interaction effect between Gender (Male and Female) and Types of crime (High crime and Low crime) with relation to Differential Personality Inventory Dimension.

	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>A1B1</i>	<i>A1B2</i>	<i>A2B1</i>	<i>A2B2</i>
1	Decisiveness	9.4667	8.3333	8.8333	9.4333
2	Responsibility	9.5	8.4333	9.1333	8.8333
3	Emotional Stability	9.4333	10.2	9.3	7.2
4	Masculinity	9.0333	9.1667	7.9667	7.2333
5	Friendliness	9.5666	8.8	8.3333	7.0666
6	Heterosexuality	8.5333	6.9333	7.2666	6.5
7	Ego-Strength	11.3	8.5666	9.1	8.9666
8	Curiosity	9.1333	7.9	7.7	8.1
9	Dominance	10	8.4333	7.9333	8.7333
10	Self-Concept	9.3333	7.6667	8.0666	7.7333

(n=120, males=60, females=60)

Table 3: Showing the result of ANOVA on Gender (SS_A), Type of crime (SS_B) with relation to Total Differential personality inventory.

<i>Source of Variance</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sum of Square</i>	<i>Mean Sum of Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Table Value</i>	<i>Level of Significant</i>
			SS/df			
SSA	1	110.2083	110.2083	0.4930	3.92/6.84	NS
SSB	1	648.675	648.675	2.9021	3.92/6.84	NS
SSAB	1	969.0083	969.0083	4.3352	3.92	0.05
SS Error	116	25928.1	223.5181			
SST	119	27655.99167				

*S= Significant or 0.05, 0.01; NS = Non-Significant

Table shows the results of ANOVA of personality of various group' F ratio for personality of all dimension with relation to gender (ASS) is 0.4930 which

is insignificant. F ratio for personality of all dimensions with relation to type of crime (BSS) is 2.9021 which is insignificant. F ratio for personality of all dimension on gender and type of crime (A*B) is 3.92 which is significant at 0.05 level.

Table 4: Gender and type of crime with Total Differential personality inventory.

	A1	A2	B1	B2
Mean	86.2	84.2833	87.5666	82.9166

Descriptive statistics shows the mean scores of personality with reference to gender and type of crime. Mean score for male is 86.2 and Mean score for female criminals is 84.2833 which is insignificant and mean score for high charged is 87.5666 and low charged is 82.9166 which is insignificant. No significant interaction effect is seen between gender and personality as well as type of crime and personality.

Table 5: Interaction effect of Gender and Type of crime with Total Differential personality inventory.

	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2
Mean	91.3666	81.0333	83.7666	84.8
N	30	30	30	30

Table shows the mean score of gender that is male criminal and female criminal and mean score of type of crime based upon high charged and low charged criminals by personality. The mean score of male high charged criminals

Graph: Bar Diagram showing mean difference of Gender (Male & Female) and Type of Crime (High Crime & Low Crime) on Total Differential personality inventory

is 91.3666, for male low charged criminals score is 81.0333. The mean score of female high charged criminals is 83.7666, for female low charged criminals is 84.8. There is no significant difference between gender and type of crime with regards to personality.

Graph shows the interaction effect of gender and type of crime. The mean score of Male high charged crime that is 91.3666 & Male low charged crime that is 81.0333. Female high charged crime that is 83.7666 & Female low charged crime that is 84.8.

Discussion

The present study has been conducted for two different groups of criminals. Objective of the study was to know whether there is a significant effect of personality in criminals going through imprisonment.

On the basis of statistical analysis there is no significant difference between gender with regards to personality of Decisiveness, Responsibility, Heterosexuality, Ego-strength, Curiosity, Self-concept and there is significant difference of personality in Emotional stability, Masculinity, Friendliness and Dominance. As well as there is no significant difference between the type of crime with regards to personality of Decisiveness, Emotional stability, Masculinity, Curiosity, Dominance and there is significant difference to personality of Responsibility, Friendliness, Heterosexuality, Ego-strength, Self-concept. Furthermore, there is no significant interaction effect between gender and type of crime in criminals with regards to personality of Responsibility, Emotional stability, Masculinity, Friendliness, Heterosexuality, Self-concept and significant interaction effect to personality of Decisiveness, Ego-strength, Curiosity, Dominance.

Here, significant difference among male and female criminals on personality and no significant difference among high charged and low charged criminals on personality and also no significant interaction effect between gender and types of crime in criminals with regards to personality.

The results indicate that male criminals conduct more crime than female criminals as well as male criminals were more prone to high charge crime than female criminals. Female criminals conduct more of low charge crime than male criminals.

Conclusion

Females are arrested less than males for all categories of crime except that of prostitution. This ratio stands true for all countries. The comparison was

conducted to assess between gender and the type of crime in criminals with regards to the role of personality. The results indicate that male criminals conduct more crime than the female criminals as well as male criminals were more prone to high charge crime than female criminals. Female criminals conduct more of low charge crime than male criminals.

Suggestions

Further research in this area is needed with larger sample size and comparison of different metropolitan cities, different states done through the research would be more meaningful.

Due to time constraint the research could study only one psychological aspect of criminals. Many more psychological aspects like: family pathology, aggression, social intelligence, parenting and many more could be analysed.

A comparative study of various age groups of criminals should be conducted.

This research could solely be conducted on juveniles.

Limitations

The present research has some limitations. This research has been conducted on small group. Hence, it cannot be generalised. The sample was selected solely from Sabarmati Jail, Ahmedabad. This research has been carried out in limited time.

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